

Digital Society: It's Foundation and Towards an Interdisciplinary Field

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Abstract:

A Digital Society is an interdisciplinary research area and a kind of progressive society that has been formed as a result of adaptation as well as integration of advanced technologies into the society and culture. Among the emerging technologies and field that responsible for developing a true Digital Society is include Information and Communication Technology (ICT), Information Science and Computing and other areas viz. Business Studies, Commerce and several areas of Humanities and Social science. Digital Society is mainly deals with the highly advanced telecommunications and wireless connectivity systems and solutions. Digital Society is mainly depends on Digital Economy which is one of the emerging concept of economic development with proper support from digital tools and technologies and depends on information, knowledge and digital products. Digital Society is mainly depends on different kind of stakeholders which include the society, technologies and content. The latest name in Digital Society is includes Internet of Things (IoT), 5G, Cloud Computing, Big Data, Human Computer Interaction and so on. There are many emerging concepts fall under the Digital Society viz. Smart Town, Smart City, Smart Villages and so many other smart and advanced services. The growing importance of technologies in the society and its interaction led the development of concept of Digital Society as a field of study. Many universities internationally have been started academic programs, events in this area. This paper is talks about the latest of Digital Society including its meaning and concept, stakeholders, characteristics and features. Paper also talks about the challenges of Digital Society including its academic potentiality.

Keywords : Digital Society, Digital Humanities, Information Technology, Information Science, Interdisciplinary, Advanced Society, India

1. Introduction: Digital Society :

A digital society is an interdisciplinary research lab and this is a progressive society that is formed as a result of the adoption and integration of Information and communication

technologies, computer science, information science and business science & the humanities at home, work, education and recreation [1],[5].

Digital society mainly deals with highly advanced telecommunications and wireless connectivity system and solutions. Digital society mainly depends on digital economy which is a concept of economic development with proper support from digital tools & technologies and depends on information knowledge & digital products [3], [4], [8].

2. Objective of the Paper

This is a basic overview and conceptual paper and basically deals with following aim and objective in brief—

- To know about the basic of Digital Society; including its meaning and features.
- To learn about the basic characteristics of Digital Society including its stakeholders in brief manner.
- To learn about the Function and Tools of such kind of society in brief manner.
- To learn about the technological affairs for the development of a Digital Society; especially Information Technology.
- To learn about the challenges and issues in respect of Digital Society in brief.
- To know about the opportunities and advantages in respect of design, development of Digital Society.
- To find out the basic technological skill requirement in respect of design, development of Digital Society.

3. Stakeholders of Digital Society

Design, development of Digital Society is deals with different stakeholders and these are rising [2], [6], [7]. Basically, Digital society depends on following stakeholders or component—

- **Society**- it includes common people, community civilization.
- **Technologies**- it includes software technology, communication technology, database technology, network technology, multimedia technology.
- **Content**- it include data, information, knowledge, documentation etc.
- **Knowledge Management**- it include knowledge organization, knowledge processing, database technology etc.

4. Tools for Digital Society

There are various tools used for building a Digital Society and among these few important are include (but not limited to)—

- Computing tools: There are many tools uses in this regard viz. *laptops, computers*
- Network tools: Among the important devices few important are *Router, switch, repeater, hub*.
- Database tools: *DMBS, database, storage device (pen drive, hard drive* etc are the core of this segment
- Communication system: Satellite system are basic and important in this
- Multimedia tools: HCI (Human Computer Interaction) system [9], [11], [13].

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5. Digital Society and Characteristics

There are various attributes of Digital Society and among these few important are include the following—

- Digital society deals with tools and technologies.
- The technologies and tools of digital society may be change.
- Some of the common technologies of digital societies are- Network technology, software technology, communication technology, database technology, multimedia technology.
- All the emerging areas are- IOT, 5G, Cloud computing, big data.
- Digital society has for many passages such as digital divide, information divide [8], [10], [13].

There are many project achieved in India like- BHOOMI, GAYANDOOT, LOKVANI, FRIENDS, E-SUVIDHA, E-CHOUPAL, Internet Sathi etc.

6. Challenges of Digital Society

India is moving towards a Digital Society; however there are many issues available for creation of a digital society. Following are some of the challenges-

- Digital society creation is purely depends on proper co-operation, co-ordination and collaboration of all stake-holders [12], [15].
- Challenges regarding as lack of proper planning of digital product uses and their applicability of common people.
- Digital society faces challenges in the unavailability of human resources and different areas of IT & IS
- Digital society establishment required proper and enough fund and budget for executing work.
- Unavailability and shortage of skilled manpower.
- Lack of policy implementation [14], [16].
- Lack of infrastructure available.
- Limited initiatives from the government bodies and ministries.
- Less involvement of common people into the Agenda.
- Unwillingness towards the project.
- Testing already implemented project.

Apart from this several others requirement are also important for creation of a Digital Society viz. digital village, digital town, digital nation (such as digital India) as a whole. The development of this society has been traces from ICT4D and its different phases also help in this regard. *Table: 1* depicted in this regard in detail.

Table: 1-Phases of ICT4D and Tools: The root for building Digital Society

Phase of ICT4D	Tools
<i>ICT4D 0.0 – (1950-1980)</i>	Computing devices
<i>ICT4D 1.0 – (1990-1990)</i>	Computer/ internet/email
<i>ICT4D 2.0 – (2000- Till)</i>	Social Networking viz.

	(Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp etc), IOT (internet of things), Cloud computing, Big data
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7. Digital literacy: The Backbone of Digital Society

Digital literacy is an important concept and area of digital society. In generally digital literate may be a person having the knowledge and skill on digital tools, digital technologies etc [15], [17]. Digital literacy may be classified as follows—

- Computer Literacy
- Network Literacy
- Web Literacy
- Internet Literacy
- Media Literacy
- Multimedia Literacy

Computer Literacy

Computer Literacy is gaining knowledge and skill on computer and its basic operations. These are very basic for the creation of Digital Society or as a attributes in Digital Society.

Network Literacy

Network Literacy is the skill and knowledge on network related affairs such as creation of network, sharing of network, network services.

Web Literacy

Web Literacy is a skill and knowledge on web related affairs such as doing the work wave browser, mark up language, net surfing, basic web management etc.

Multimedia Literacy

Multimedia Literacy is the skill and knowledge on multimedia related affairs. It is the job and knowledge on basic of multimedia application features, skill sets on basic multimedia packages.

Apart from these, Literacy in digital age we have Literacy related to several areas; for example, media Literacy, information Literacy [12], [16].

Due to the importance of Digital Society many university have started the Digital Society as an Educational Program and Courses and among these few important are The University of Edinburg, Central University of Rajasthan, International Institute of Information Technology, Bangalore. These institutes are offers MSc in Digital Society program. However many university have started program on Allied areas called as following—

- Digital Humanities
- Digital Sociology
- IT in Society etc

8. Conclusion

The concept of Digital Society is rising and developing rapidly, the growth of Information Science and Technology applications helps in building Digital Infrastructure which includes improvement of Network Infrastructure, Web Infrastructure, Database Infrastructure, Content Infrastructure and so on. The advancement of newer and emerging technologies viz. Cloud Computing, Big Data Analytics, Human Computer Interaction, User Experience Designing, Intelligent Systems etc. The content is increasing day by day and in here Digital Society is important aspect to be noted.

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